

EXPLORING THE PRACTICES, EXPERIENCES AND CHALLENGES OF TEACHERS IN USING DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION IN AN INCLUSION SETTING

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Exploring the Practices, Experiences and Challenges of Teachers in Using Differentiated Instruction in an Inclusion Setting

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Abstract

This study explores the practices, experiences and challenges of teachers in using differentiated instruction (DI) in an inclusion setting through a qualitative research design which involved interviewing 17 participants, including 12 certified teachers and 5 paraprofessionals. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes and insights. Themes for DI as practiced by the teachers and other teaching personnel emerge such as strategies for optimizing learning outcomes that includes clustered subthemes of hands-on learning, art integration, project based learning and low floor high ceiling, implementation of the What I Need (WIN) time program that includes sub themes on different learning stations and small groups based on learners' abilities and offering multiple learning pathways. Teachers' experiences in using DI shows varying themes on their perceptions on DI and WIN time program, recurring theme of implementation of DI and their experiential insights on DI. Teachers report mixed experiences on DI with most valuing its impact and significantly enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes when implemented effectively but with some finding DI overwhelming and challenging due to time constraints and varied learners' needs. Themes that emerge as teachers face challenges in using DI are the limited time for planning and preparation, ineffective time management and implementation and issues on class management. In resolving such challenges, solutions based themes emerge such as setting expectations, reassignment of small groups, enhancing instructional engagement, collaborative teaching and team support and continuing professional development and training. These findings provided implications for practice for refining differentiated instruction practices within inclusive classrooms.

Keywords: *special education, inclusive education, qualitative method, south dakota, USA*

Introduction

Perspectives on education are constantly changing on a global scale to emphasize the value of inclusive education. According to this perspective, the innovation in inclusive teaching methods is mostly concentrated on lowering the obstacles faced by learners who are marginalized in certain educational environments, particularly by learners with special educational needs (LSENs). This has made it extremely necessary for all teachers in general and even more so with special education (SpEd) teachers to use inclusive teaching methods in order to guarantee that each and everyone in the classroom receives meaningful, learner-centered training. Therefore, in order to meet the unique requirements of LSENs, inclusive education requires teachers to use a variety of instructional methodologies, including differentiated instruction (DI).

Resource teachers in the SpEd department at McLaughlin Elementary School were assigned to learners by grade level, resulting in caseloads that included a range of disabilities as defined by the South Dakota Department of Education (2022). These disabilities included Specific Learning Disabilities (SLD), which affect a learner's ability to understand or use language in reading, writing, and math; Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), impacting both verbal and nonverbal communication and social interactions; and Emotional Disabilities (ED), characterized by an inability to learn not explained by other factors, difficulties in relationships, inappropriate behavior or feelings, pervasive unhappiness, or physical symptoms related to personal or school issues. Developmental Delay (DD) involves severe delays, defined as functioning two or more standard deviations below the mean in one developmental area or 1.5 standard deviations below the mean in two or more areas. Cognitive Disability (CD) is marked by significantly below-average intellectual functioning with deficits in adaptive behavior, typically evident before age eighteen and requiring assessment of intellectual and adaptive skills. Speech or Language Impairment (SLI) includes communication disorders such as stuttering, impaired articulation, language disorders, or voice disorders. Other Health Impairment (OHI) refers to limited strength, vitality, or alertness due to chronic or acute health issues, such as heart conditions, asthma, ADHD, sickle cell anemia, epilepsy, or diabetes, which adversely affects educational performance.

In this setting, the learners participated in What I Need (WIN) Time, an hour-long session in the general education classroom where they receive personalized lessons and practice activities tailored to their current level of understanding. This time is structured for the small groups of learners to rotate across four stations which focus on different subjects and skill areas. Research supports that combining effective whole-group instruction with small group settings and individualized teaching is the most effective way to accelerate their learning and address diverse educational needs (Henderson & Walker, 2023).

Since it takes into account the different features, interests, and developmental capacities of each learner, it can be difficult to design instruction that makes accommodations for each learner's differences. Given the complexity of accommodating learner variability, it is imperative that educators differentiate instruction and make pedagogical decisions that consistently advance SpEd's main objective, which is to include all learners in the Least Restrictive Environment (LRE), a setting where they can learn as much as possible in an

environment that is as appropriate as possible.

As a result, schools have gradually switched from remote learning to in-person education. Because of the two-year lapse in in-person instruction, learners consequently return to school with academic and competence impairments. Younger learners are more impacted, particularly if they require supervised closeness to study.

Due to the ongoing educational gap, there is a continuing need for more research in the field of education, which has put SpEd teachers under pressure to review and acquire new concepts related to DI. The persistent problem is that SpEd teachers are finding it extremely difficult to gradually return to in-person instruction after the pandemic and to shift to remote learning. Because of this, individuals are more likely to experience burnout because their jobs necessitate retaining more paperwork and records.

DI is the most crucial component of instruction for learners with Individualized Education Plans (IEPs). Teachers adapt learner variability to the curriculum on a daily basis so that children can respond, learn, and ultimately reach their individual IEP goals. Sadly, most teachers face difficulties differentiating instruction due to a lack of professional development opportunities and a multitude of shortcomings in educational resources. This is particularly true when it comes to tailoring teaching strategies to the varied needs of learners. It can be difficult and complex to accommodate learner diversity, therefore educators must be innovative in offering several ways for learners to acquire knowledge and ideas for learning.

It is a fact that each individual learns and copes with the environment in unique ways. Various forms of individual learners do exist. No two learners learn in the exact same way as each other. Teachers have to be able to see the strengths of the learners' needs rather than focus on their weaknesses. Creating opportunities for all learners, by enriching the classroom through their MI, techniques and approaches. Because there are learners who need DI for them to cope with the discussions. Thus, for learners with exceptionalities, DI is indeed a great help for them.

This opened a sight of interest to delve into DI to see if it is being catered well to the learners and to know how it affects the performance of those who are receiving it in an inclusive school setting. In the United States, the legal basis for inclusion in education is primarily grounded in federal laws and regulations that mandate equal educational opportunities for all learners, including those with disabilities. The key piece of legislation that addresses the inclusion of learners with disabilities is the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) which is a federal law that ensures that LSENSs have access to a free appropriate public education (FAPE) in the LRE.

SpEd in the United States focuses on helping children with disabilities learn. Federal law requires that learners who receive SpEd be taught alongside their non-disabled peers as much as possible. By law, schools are required to give SpEd in the LRE. This means the starting point for discussion should be the support your child needs to succeed in a general education classroom (SD Law, 2022). Diverse learners and varied learning styles entail a differentiation of instruction to further maximize a learner's learning potential. The importance of such is something worth studying and if it works for every child. Differentiation must always be "a way up" and never "a way out". Its goal is to maximize individual growth and success.

This research is geared toward finding out how DI is being practiced at McLaughlin Elementary School, an inclusive school setting in McLaughlin School District, McLaughlin, South Dakota and how effective it is on the general education learners and for learners on individualized education programs especially in the elementary level. It is the researcher's aim to understand the teachers' point of view and know the varied implementation of DI, hence this study.

Research Questions

The research explored the practices, experiences and challenges of the teachers in using DI in an inclusion setting at McLaughlin Elementary School, McLaughlin School District, McLaughlin, South Dakota, USA for school year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How is DI practiced by the teachers and other teaching personnel at McLaughlin Elementary School?
2. What are the teachers' experiences in using DI?
3. What are some of the challenges teachers faced in implementing DI?
4. How are these challenges resolved?
5. Based on this study, what implications are formulated to improve the school's use of DI?

Literature Review

In exploring the practices, experiences, and challenges of teachers in using DI in an inclusion setting, this study was structured on the lenses of Howard Gardner's (1983) Multiple Intelligence theory, Lev Vygotsky's (1934) concept on the Socio-Cultural theory and Zone of Proximal Development as well as the Scaffolding theory introduced by Jerome Bruner (1978) with its origin from the work of Vygotsky. In the legal aspect, the Individual with disabilities Education Act (2004), Free Appropriate Public Education (2004), Every Student Succeeds Act (2015), and South Dakota Law supported this study.

The Multiple Intelligence (MI) theory focused on the expansion of the concept of intelligence to also include such areas as music, spatial relations, and interpersonal knowledge in addition to mathematical and linguistic ability (Timmins, 2019). Howard Gardner

believed how humans have different kinds of mental abilities that make up different kinds of intelligence which he called multiple intelligences and defines such as "the capacity to solve problems or to fashion products that are valued in one or more cultural settings". Gardner (2021) identified eight intelligences: linguistic intelligence, logical-mathematical intelligence, spatial intelligence, musical intelligence, bodily-kinesthetic intelligence, naturalistic intelligence, interpersonal intelligence, and intrapersonal intelligence. To effectively personalize or differentiate instruction, it is important that teachers must deeply understand the theories behind Howard Gardner's theory of MI, as it helped teachers tailor their instruction to accommodate the diverse ways people learn (Morgan, 2021).

Nevertheless, despite the theory not being readily accepted within academic psychology, it has however met with a strongly positive response from many educators. According to Ferrero et al. (2021), schools traditionally focus on academic skills such as reading and mathematics, resulting in other areas such as music or physical expression to be neglected. But because of the mentioned theory, educators have started to recognize that all children are unique and valuable, regardless of their capacities, which led many children to grab the opportunities to explore their true interests and talents. The theory thus implies that educators should recognize and teach to a broader range of talents and skills. Another implication is that teachers should structure the presentation of material in a style which engages most or all of the intelligences. Schools have often sought to help learners develop a sense of accomplishment and self-confidence and this theory provides a theoretical foundation for recognizing the different abilities and talents of learners (Timmins, 2019). Given this significant contribution to education, it's understandable why many teachers enthusiastically adopt MIT-inspired classroom interventions (Ferrero et al., 2021).

To support the theory, Mardiana and Indiaty (2020) conducted a study that supports Gardner by demonstrating how identifying learners' intelligence types through standardized tools enables teachers to select instructional methods that best meet learners' needs. Ganiev (2021) further highlights that a learner's educational opportunities are influenced by both genetics and upbringing, aligning with the nature versus nurture debate. Consequently, by applying Gardner's theory can significantly enhance a learner's potential since educators can create an engaging learning environment that maximizes learners' ability to process information and reach their full capacity (Bowker, 2020).

Additionally, sociocultural theory (SCT) is a concept developed by Soviet psychologist and social constructivist Lev Vygotsky which consequently focuses more on social interaction as an aid to learning – arguing that although naturally children will develop, but if left alone it is not to their full potential (McLeod, 2023). Social interaction is fundamental to the development of cognition that leads not only to increased levels of knowledge, but actually changes a child's thoughts and behaviors (Marens, 2023). As suggested by Arcidiacono and Baucal (2020), if two individuals engage in an activity using different cultural tools, their mindsets and practices will differ, which highlights the significant influence of these artifacts on shaping one's cognition and behavior.

To add, as cited by McLeod (2023) in his article, Vygotsky (1978) believed that much important learning by the child occurs through social interaction with a skillful tutor. The tutor may model behaviors and/or provide verbal instructions for the child. Rahmatirad's (2020) study concludes that socio-cultural factors are essential for children's cognitive development and understanding SCT helps teachers design tasks that facilitate language learning by integrating cognitive and social perspectives. In order to achieve the highest level of development possible, parents should expose their children to a variety of social situations, since each interaction is considered a learning experience; the more experiences that a child has, the richer their world becomes.

Significantly, a pivotal study by Robertson (2021) underscores that effective educational transitions for young learners require intentional collaboration among teachers, active involvement of families, and robust support from early childhood education administrators. The presence of trusted adults is crucial in guiding children through these transitions. Similarly, Sibakova (2023) found that the roles of teachers and parents in fostering imaginative activities and creative experiences significantly enhance learners' self-expression and contribute to their overall development.

Furthermore, Vygotsky (1986) believes that the interaction of concepts between everyday interactions before school and scientific concepts learned during school is important and that the latter play a leading role in reshaping spontaneous concepts and developing holistic thinking, an act that teachers can directly influence through collective educational activities (Margolis, 2020). McLeod (2023) cited that the zone of proximal development (ZPD) has been defined by Vygotsky (1978) as: "the distance between the actual developmental level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem-solving under adult guidance, or in collaboration with more capable peers". In addition to that, learning occurs most effectively on the higher plane of thinking through competent adults interacting with a child in a theoretical zone of development called the ZPD. Zaretsky (2021) acknowledges that challenges are an essential part of learning since these can push children to attempt tasks beyond their current abilities. Vygotsky (1978) also argues that this ZPD gap between potential and the actual learning can be bridged only through collaboration with adults and the learners. When faced with enough difficulties, children will soon recognize their limits and seek adult assistance. As a result, if a cooperative relationship is established, the child and adult work together to find effective ways to address difficulties, correct mistakes, and prevent future errors. Each successfully overcome challenge becomes a step in learning, promoting significant development (Zaretsky, 2021). In educational settings, the concept of ZPD has inspired practices like cooperative learning, DI and scaffolded learning experiences (McLeod, 2023).

Consequently, given that the ZPD was developed to address the need for education to nurture not only the intellectual but also the physical and moral capacities of learners, it was discovered that a child's learning potential is not confined to their current abilities.

Instead, this potential can be greatly expanded through collaborative interactions within their learning environment (Kostogriz & Veresov, 2021). Ofori-Attah (2021) further substantiates this by demonstrating that integrating ZPD into classroom practice fosters social interaction and significantly enhances learning outcomes.

To clarify, while ZPD has widely been used interchangeably with the term scaffolding, Vygotsky never used this term in his writing and was introduced by Wood, Bruner and Ross (1976). Both Bruner and Vygotsky placed an important emphasis on a child's social environment and agreed that adults should play an active role in assisting the child's learning (McLeod, 2023). McLeod (2023) further wrote that Jerome Bruner (1978) like Vygotsky, emphasized the social nature of learning, citing that other people should help a child develop skills through the process of scaffolding. According to Bruner (1978), "scaffolding refers to the steps taken to reduce the degrees of freedom in carrying out some tasks so that the child can concentrate on the difficult skill she is in the process of acquiring" (McLeod, 2023). Scaffolding additionally in the education sense is an effective educational strategy that involves the teacher providing support structures to help learners master their skills that are beyond their current level. Bruner's model requires the teacher to be actively involved in lessons and thus providing cognitive scaffolding which then facilitates the learning on the part of the learner (McLeod, 2023). The purpose of this scaffolded support is for the child to be able to achieve higher development skills through tasks being simplified, encouraging or motivating the child, highlighting important tasks or errors and through modelling.

Furthermore, Sarmiento-Campos et al. (2022) demonstrated that learners exposed to scaffolding techniques, particularly interactive and intervening strategies that encourage engagement with language in a conversational context, experienced significant improvements in their speaking skills. In a different domain, Monteiro et al. (2020) found that consistent and tiered scaffolding in science education notably enhanced learners' engagement and understanding. As scaffolding was progressively implemented at various levels, learners increasingly took responsibility for their own learning, reflecting the effectiveness of this approach in fostering greater autonomy and deeper comprehension.

With that said, it was imperative for this study to consider the legal landscape as well. Taking into account the legal perspectives can provide a comprehensive understanding of the broader implications and applications of the research findings within the legal context.

To start it off, as the value of inclusivity became increasingly apparent, differentiated education underwent a steady transformation. Differentiated education has its roots in the days when a single teacher oversaw learners of all ages in a single classroom (Tursunboevna, 2022). Learners' different talents led to learning gaps, as evidenced by the results of achievement exams. The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) established legislation to ensure that kids of all abilities can access education equally, as long as teachers use DI. Subsequent amendments reflected in the IDEA, have led to an increased emphasis on access to the general education curriculum and accountability for the achievement of learners with disabilities (US Department of Education). In 2004, the IDEA reauthorization aligned the IDEA with the No Child Left Behind Act requirements calling for early intervening services for children not currently identified as needing SpEd but who need additional academic and behavioral support to succeed in a general education environment and greater accountability and improved educational outcomes (US DEPED, IDEA).

To add, a policy guideline issued on Free Appropriate Public Education (FAPE) by the Office of Special Education and Rehabilitative Services (OSERS) under the US DOE states that for an eligible child with a disability under the IDEA must be aligned with the State's academic content standards for the grade in which the child is enrolled. Research has demonstrated that children with disabilities who struggle in reading and mathematics can successfully learn grade-level content and make significant academic progress when appropriate instruction, services, and support are provided (Federal Register, 2023). Here is where DI is crucial as an accommodation support to be implemented in the inclusive general education classroom.

Furthermore, South Dakota Law (2022) expresses the importance of SpEd as a federal program that assists local schools in addressing the needs of LSENs wherein each child receives support depending on their unique needs. This is geared towards achieving the main goal which is to make sure LSENs have the tools and instruction they need to be successful in school. In 2022-2023, the US DOE reported more than 66% of children with disabilities are in general education classrooms 80% or more of their school day. This shows classrooms have become more inclusive, thus presenting the need for instruction in the general education curriculum to be more accessible so that significant progress can be made in improving educational outcomes. In addition, the IDEA Part B regulations define the term "specially designed instruction," the critical element in the definition of "special education," as "adapting, as appropriate to the needs of an eligible child, the content, methodology, or delivery of instruction to address the unique needs of the child that result from the child's disability and to ensure access of the child to the general curriculum.

Additionally, the Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA), formerly known as the No Child Left Behind Act (NCLB), reauthorizes the Elementary and Secondary Education Act and shifts more control to states and local districts, allowing them to set their own goals and accountability systems for their learner's performance (Every Student Succeeds Act, 2015). It also promotes the use of evidence-based interventions, provides more funding for early childhood education, and ensures protections for LSENs. The South Dakota Department of Education (SD DOE) plans to support the said law by conducting a Comprehensive Needs Assessment (CNA) every three years with an external entity which aims to identify the unique educational needs of the state's migrant children and find suitable services to help these children. The districts will perform individual needs assessments to determine the needs of migrant learners and how these needs align with SD DOE priorities and through this process, the state will be able to determine essential data such as specific needs by grade level, key academic areas, instructional settings, materials, and staffing requirements. Additionally, SD DOE permits districts

the use of the discrepancy model for identifying learners with learning disabilities and can use the Response to Intervention (RTI) model for eligibility determination by submitting a formal proposal on how they will meet the eligibility requirements. To support learners with disabilities, SD DOE has engaged various stakeholders to focus the State Systemic Improvement Plan (SSIP) on improving reading proficiency among LSENs entering fourth grade, aligning with the goal of ensuring college and career readiness for all learners (South Dakota Department of Education, 2017).

Also, today's education, despite following an "inclusive" approach, is still a system of teachers delivering a standardized curriculum to entire classes which results in overlooking the individual differences among learners including their cognitive abilities, learning styles, interests, and prior knowledge, all of which are factors when it comes to their educational experiences and outcomes. Fortunately, due to the support of psychological theories and empirical research, there has been a recent growing recognition of the need for a more individualized approach to education which emphasizes that effective teaching can be done when content and pedagogy are tailored to each learner's unique characteristics and needs to optimize engagement, learning, and academic success (Barakayevna, 2024). Determining student support based on the learner's needs and classroom demands is an ideal vehicle for implementing DI in the classroom.

To put it into perspective, in the US, the Multilevel DI Framework for Inclusive Education which comprises four levels: universally designed instruction, culturally responsive pedagogies, assistive technologies, and a collaborative team approach, is utilized to support educators in addressing the diverse needs of all learners, from those with significant disabilities to those who are gifted, within general education settings (Lawrence-Brown & Abkowitz, 2023). Lawrence-Brown and Abkowitz (2023) wrote that individualized supports and services integrated into general classrooms often yield equal or superior results for LSENs and benefit the entire class.

Specifically, in South Dakota, the school districts must go through an evaluation procedure wherein the process include tests and other evaluation materials provided in the child's native language or an understood mode of communication, unless not feasible, with standardized tests validated for their specific purpose and administered by trained personnel; tests assessing specific educational needs, not just general intelligence; tests administered to accurately reflect a child's aptitude or achievement level, not influenced by sensory, manual, or speaking impairments unless those are the factors being measured; multiple procedures used for determining eligibility and educational programs; a variety of assessment tools and strategies, including parental input, used to determine if the child has a disability and to develop the child's IEP, ensuring involvement in the general curriculum or appropriate activities for preschool children; technically sound instruments and strategies assessing cognitive, behavioral, physical, or developmental factors to determine educational needs; comprehensive assessments covering all areas related to the suspected disability, such as health, vision, hearing, social and emotional status, intelligence, academic performance, communication, and motor abilities; and evaluations identifying all SpEd and related service's needs (South Dakota Department of Education, 2022). According to Structural Learning (2023), effective differentiation relies on numerous considerations and techniques including flexible grouping and ongoing assessment, making it a powerful instructional strategy. To implement differentiation successfully, teachers must understand their learners' strengths, weaknesses, learning styles, and interests. Additionally, it is also essential for teachers to create an effective lesson plan while considering the main principles for doing so by focusing on skills over content, employing multiple strategies for the same skill, and offering a range of activities to engage diverse learners (Structural Learning, 2023).

To support, studies have shown the positive outcomes of DI. Recognizing that LSENs are part of a broader spectrum of human functioning, it is crucial for an education system to acknowledge this continuum. Such a system should provide appropriate services to all learners, addressing their shared needs for relatedness, autonomy, and competence in learning whilst ensuring that participation in education should be the primary focus when planning changes to educational settings and services (Arcidiacono & Baucal, 2020). The study done by Am et al. (2023) concludes that DI is indeed a valuable strategy for enhancing learning across various educational levels with its effectiveness closely linked to the specific educational context and environment of a given country, emphasizing that its success and optimal outcomes are highly sensitive to the unique contextual factors and educational settings in which it is implemented. Interestingly, one study found that teachers had positive experiences when undergoing their individual learning activities and they recognized the importance of collaborative knowledge development within the school, unanimously agreeing that successful implementation of DI requires increased collaboration among staff (Gheysens et al., 2020).

However, in the study conducted by Lavania et al. (2020), it has been found that one of the challenges in DI implementation is a lack of knowledge among teachers towards the practice. Another issue found in another study is how the teaching staffs address the needs of their learners unevenly and tend to standardize their teaching, possibly due to their institution's curriculum, which lacks practical experience and a systematic framework when it comes to addressing all pupils' needs in the classroom appropriately (Obrovská et al., 2023). Similar findings were stated in the study done by Onyishi and Sefotho (2020) wherein teachers' need for further information on developing assessment rubrics, managing large classes while implementing DI, maintaining curriculum rigor, adapting classroom structures for small group work, and receiving more training on DI and diverse learning aids were prominently emphasized.

Further, this study is further supported also by the concept of explicit teaching by Anita Archer. As written by Rolf and Slocum (2023), the utilization of explicit instruction typically features a user's manual, mastery tests, student materials, and scripted lessons that are well-organized, focuses on critical skills, and uses clear, concise, and consistent language for step-by-step demonstrations. Early lessons include scaffolding to ensure high levels of learner success and examples and non-examples illustrate the application of skills, and

learners actively practice these concepts (Rolf & Slocum, 2023). This concept also offers a framework for intensifying instruction where teachers ensure learner engagement by frequently asking relevant questions and closely monitoring their performance during lessons in order to adjust instruction as needed such as using specific error correction procedures, providing additional targeted practice, removing scaffolding, and giving specific praise (Rolf & Slocum, 2023).

To encapsulate, the researcher employs the theoretical lenses of Gardner's Multiple Intelligence theory, Vygotsky's Sociocultural theory and Zone of Proximal Development, and Bruner's Scaffolding theory to provide a thorough understanding of how differentiated instruction is implemented in an inclusive setting. The integration of these frameworks, along with the legal perspectives of IDEA, FAPE, and ESSA, underscores the necessity for teachers to adapt their instruction to meet the cognitively, socially, and emotionally diverse needs of learners, fostering meaningful learning and promoting inclusivity in education.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research method to gain insights into the experiences of teachers and paraprofessionals (teacher's assistants) within the inclusion setting of general education classrooms. The aim was to explore DI, explicit instruction, and teaching strategies by utilizing thematic analysis as complementary methods.

The qualitative phenomenological approach was chosen to illuminate specific phenomena by examining how they were perceived by the participants in the situation. This approach involved gathering in-depth information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews and participant discussions. The goal was to represent these experiences from the perspective of the research participants.

Gill (2020) defined phenomenology as both a philosophical approach and a qualitative research methodology that investigates the structures of experience and consciousness. The term combines the Greek suffix "-ology," meaning 'study,' with "phenomenon," referring to the objects or events that appear in our consciousness. In research, phenomenology focuses on understanding how these phenomena manifest in human experience and how individuals perceive and interpret them. By exploring the subjective dimensions of experience, phenomenology aims to reveal the essential nature of how people experience and make sense of the world around them. This approach is particularly valuable for examining lived experiences and gaining insights into the meanings that individuals attach to their experiences (Gill, 2020).

Participants

The research participants in this study consisted of certified teaching professionals with valid teaching credentials and classified personnel who provide instructional or student support services but do not hold a teaching certification. These individuals were selected from McLaughlin Elementary School across various grade levels in general education classrooms, with a minimum of one year of experience.

Participants were chosen using stratified sampling to ensure adequate representation of both categories of school personnel according to specific eligibility criteria. Additionally, the purposive sampling method was employed to include key participants who could provide expertise relevant to the research questions.

Table 1 provides a general overview of the participants, including their employment category and the number of research respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Participants*

Type	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Staff type / Category	Certified	12	70.59
	Classified	5	29.41
	Total	17	100

Instrument

This research utilized data sources including interviews, emails, and written narratives, to examine the various ways and techniques through which teachers and paraprofessionals practiced differentiation in the school. The interview questionnaire employed a semi-structured format divided into three parts: introduction, interview proper, and closing. The introduction section outlined the study's significance, established rapport, and gathered background information. The interview proper featured in-depth, open-ended questions about teaching strategies, experiences, and challenges related to managing small groups within an inclusive classroom setting while using DI. The closing section addressed recommendations, additional concerns, and any information related to DI or the study. Interview proceedings were recorded and transcribed to facilitate the analysis and interpretation of respondents' responses.

Procedure

This portion included three stages; the pre-data gathering stage, data gathering stage, and the post-data gathering stage.

Pre-data gathering stage. The researcher first obtained the school principal's approval to schedule the interviews. Profiling of the

certified and classified teaching personnel at McLaughlin Elementary School was conducted initially. Informed Consent were sent to each participant and they were given orientation as to how the interview will proceed. Every participant was asked of her most convenient time to be interviewed. They were made to understand that in case they would like to back out, then they can.

Data gathering stage. After all preliminary preparations, the most important activity followed. Individual interview with the teachers and paraprofessionals regarding their implementation of DI followed. The interview was recorded with prior information. Ample time was given for every participant in order to get the needed information from each one of them.

Post-data gathering procedure. After the interview, all data gathered was transcribed. Answers were clustered, coded, and themes were formulated for every cluster of answers. Presentation of data, analysis and interpretation was made.

Data Analysis

The researcher employed the thematic analysis method by Braun and Clarke (2019) for qualitative research. This was used to identify, analyze, and interpret the data collected from the interviews such as the transcripts and responses as well as what was gathered with reference to the key principles of DI proposed by Tomlinson (2006) and explicit instruction by Archer (2011) to answer the problems stated. This method also focused on identifying and interpreting recurring patterns or themes within textual data that were collected that provided meaning or significance. As cited by Campbell et. Al (2021), here is a description of reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019) within the context of statistical treatment:

Data Familiarization. This process was utilized when a researcher immerses oneself in data to understand content while searching for patterns and recognizing and giving meaning begins.

Initial coding was generated. This was done in the beginning with organizing data into meaningful groups to form initial codes with every particular data given focus and attention. This initial coding was either descriptive or interpretive.

Initial theme was generated. Codes were then grouped together based on similarities or relationships to form broader themes and the meaning of relationships between initial codes was identified.

Reviewing the theme. This was done through reviewing data sets and looked into as a whole. More of identifying repetitive patterns and redefining data to support themes.

Naming and further redefining of the theme. Further exploration and interpretation of each theme was being done within the data. This involved providing detailed descriptions of each theme, including illustrative examples and supporting evidence in order to have a more cohesive and organized data.

Production of report. The researcher then validated the identified themes through iterative review and discussion, ensuring that these themes accurately reflect the data and capture the essence of participants' experiences or perspectives. This was where data was interpreted in relation to the research questions or objectives, providing insights, explanations, or implications relevant to the study.

Ethical Considerations

This research adhered to ethical guidelines, emphasizing participant confidentiality and well-being. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and measures were implemented to ensure their anonymity. The researcher remained mindful of the potentially sensitive nature of the classroom experiences of both respondents and learners, and resources for additional support were provided as needed.

Results and Discussion

This qualitative study investigated the experiences of teachers and paraprofessionals in inclusive general education classrooms, focusing on differentiated instruction (DI), explicit instruction, and teaching strategies at McLaughlin Elementary School, McLaughlin School District, McLaughlin, South Dakota, USA for school year 2023-2024. Employing thematic analysis, the research involved purposive sampling in the selection of 17 participants, 12 certified teachers and 5 classified staff, who were interviewed with in-depth, open-ended questions. These interviews delved into the teaching strategies employed by the participants, highlighting how they approach the complexities of working in an inclusive classroom. The teachers shared insights into both their successes and struggles when working with learners who had diverse needs. Additionally, the interviews explored the challenges they faced in implementing DI, managing group dynamics, and ensuring that all learners remained engaged and supported in a setting that fosters inclusivity. The collected data were meticulously reviewed, coded, and analyzed to identify key themes: teaching strategies in inclusive settings, perspectives on the WIN (What I Need) Time program as well as their practices and experiences, the challenges in implementing differentiated instruction, and the solutions and recommendations for effective practice. Ultimately, the study synthesized insights on instructional strategies, challenges, and effective solutions related to differentiated instruction in inclusive classrooms. Implications for practice were formulated.

This section delved into the qualitative data gathered from in-depth interviews conducted with selected teachers from the participating school, focusing on their experiences with DI in the inclusive setting. The researcher explored various elements of their professional

lives through these interviews, which discussed, but were not necessarily limited to, their teaching experiences, instructional strategies, and perspectives on DI. The study also examined the challenges these teachers encountered and the strategies they employed to address these challenges effectively.

To achieve a thorough analysis, the researcher carefully organized and transcribed the oral narratives into written form and familiarized themselves with the data by repeatedly reading and reviewing the transcripts to gain a comprehensive understanding. Recurring themes and significant elements were noted, which guided the researcher in developing a coding system based on the research questions. This process enabled the identification of major themes and patterns, allowing for the comparison and contrast of different narratives to recognize possible variations and consistencies. This analysis provided a nuanced understanding of how DI was implemented and perceived in their educational settings, identifying four distinct cluster themes. The first three cluster themes encompassed three emerging themes each, while the fourth cluster theme comprised five emerging themes.

DI As Practiced By The Teachers And Other Teaching Personnel At McLaughlin Elementary School

The study investigated the teaching practices employed by teachers in the inclusive setting, concentrating on the varied approaches and methods used to address the diverse needs of their learners. It uncovered how teachers, drawing from their own diverse backgrounds akin to those of their learners, adjust their instructional practices to foster an inclusive educational environment. By delving into the strategies of the teaching staff, the research aimed to uncover the breadth of their working styles and habits, which reflect their adaptability and responsiveness to the unique challenges posed by a diverse student body. From the detailed personal testimonies of the participants, these themes were formed: Strategies for Optimizing Learning Outcomes, Implementation of the WIN Time Program, and Offering Multiple Learning Pathways.

Theme 1: Strategies for Optimizing Learning Outcomes

This theme shone light into the different strategies the teachers used in their lesson. What distinguished a teacher's unique approach was the pedagogy they adopt, reflecting their personal philosophy and educational values. The number of years a teacher has taught does not dictate the effectiveness of their methods, as educational practices evolve with time, continual adjustments and innovations are bound to happen. The remarkable aspect of teaching was that there was no universally "right" or "wrong" technique; the ultimate goal was to facilitate meaningful learning. At McLaughlin Elementary School, despite the array of teaching strategies available, certain methods have emerged as particularly effective and preferred by the teachers.

Hands on Learning

This testament underscored the significant role teachers play in achieving better classroom outcomes. Vale and Barbosa (2023) demonstrated that learners highly value experiences that promote cognitive, social, and physical engagement in developing diverse concepts and skills. The study highlighted that active learning, which facilitated collaborative work through hands-on strategies, led to the refinement of various methods for addressing tasks. These preferred strategies not only reflected the collective experience of the teachers but also demonstrated their unwavering commitment to optimizing learner learning outcomes. With that said, it was almost impossible to detach active hands on learning from DI as expressed by this participant:

– *"I'm definitely hands on, get into the dirt."* **P14**

Art Integration

Additionally, learners were able to reflect on their own decisions, mistakes, and challenges within a supportive environment, enhancing their overall learning experience (Vale & Barbosa, 2023). Another strategy which was art integration has been mentioned by the same participant through their statement:

– *"I'm really strong on art integration. So using art as a way to understand concepts and to help meet like those benchmark understandings and things like that."* **P14**

Keeping in mind that these learners have their preferences when it comes to their learning, there were instances where teachers would touch on different variations on how they deliver their lessons, one of which was through art. Art integration, as Wan et al. (2020) described, involves deliberately linking concepts and skills from the arts with other academic subjects. This approach contrasted with traditional art education, which focused on teaching specific arts subjects, such as visual arts, music, dance, and drama, based on standards, delivered by certified arts specialists, and often followed a sequential curriculum.

Project Based Learning

In the classroom, some teachers also adapted their lesson delivery to include strategies like Project-Based Learning (PBL) including this participant:

– *"So yeah, we try to do a lot of [...] project based learning. [...] This year I got deeper into the project based learning because of another side project that I'm helping with."* **P15**

It could be a challenge to allow learners to become motivated in classes and keep them on task for the reason that there were strategies that aim to remedy such issues. PBL which Smith (2022) defined as an approach that encourages learners to plan, create, and design their projects, allowing them to follow their own interests and take control of their learning process. This strategy shifted the role of the teacher from a traditional instructor to a facilitator of learning where they guide learners in their inquiries, help them to refine their questions, provide resources, and offer feedback throughout the project, creating a dynamic and collaborative relationship between the teacher and their learners (Almulla, 2020).

Low floor, High ceiling

Another strategy was used by the mentioned participant which was called the “low floor, high ceiling” or Low Threshold High Ceiling (LTHC) as they quote:

– “So, um I try to do, there's this buzzword in math, it's called low floor, high ceiling. So it kind of means like everyone can start the task but different kids can take it to different levels.” **P15**

DIs aimed for equity where learners were expected to achieve their learning goals through their own pace and in a method appropriate for their needs and capabilities which can be done through the strategy mentioned above. LFHC was designed to help learners become capable and confident by providing accessible opportunities for complex lessons (NRICH Team, 2019). Utilizing this approach eliminated the division of learners into those working on basic versus advanced material, fostering a more inclusive environment where everyone has the opportunity to share and learn from different approaches and can encourage learners to showcase their abilities rather than highlighting their limitations (NRICH Team, 2019).

As noted by Killen and O’Toole (2023), a teacher’s style was profoundly influenced by their learners’ age, educational needs, skill levels, commitment, and the subject matter they teach. This specificity meant that teaching practices were highly contextual; strategies that were effective in one setting may not necessarily succeed in another. Thus, teachers must adapt their methods to align with the unique characteristics and requirements of their learners and teaching environment.

Theme 2: Implementation of the WIN Time Program

The implementation of WIN Time at McLaughlin Elementary School stood out as a pioneering approach to DI, capturing considerable attention for its effectiveness in meeting the diverse needs of learners. Under the strategic leadership of the current principal, this initiative was meticulously designed to ensure that each learner received highly personalized instruction. During WIN time, learners engaged in tailored lessons and practice activities that directly aligned with their individual levels of understanding and specific educational requirements. This targeted method not only enhanced the learning experience for each learner but also reflected a deep commitment to educational equity, where every learner was given the tools and support necessary to thrive like the rest of their fellow learners (Henderson & Walker, 2023).

Different Learning Stations

This program, conducted in an hour-long session within the general education classroom, exemplified a strategic approach to DI. During this time, learners were organized into small groups and rotated across four stations, each facilitated by different teaching staff who specialized in various subjects and skill areas. The participants had various ways on how they organized these stations which can be read through the following statements:

– “So my four stations are para led worksheets, then my station which goes between reading and writing, then there's [redacted] table. [...] My fourth center is usually on an independent worksheet.” **P01**

– “During 'WIN time', the speaker has a teacher-led group working on current skills, a computer program group [...] an interventionist group for past skills, and an independent practice group.” **P05**

– “And then, and then they go to [redacted] station who also reinforces whatever skill that they are working on. So they get 13 to 14 to 15 minutes of that CVC here.” **P08**

Based on participant feedback, the researcher identified that each station was led by distinct individuals, typically including a teacher, a paraprofessional or an interventionist. These educators delivered their lessons according to their expertise and the specific needs of the learners during the time that they were given. Additionally, one station was designated for independent work, allowing learners to complete tasks autonomously and another station for skills set practice programs and curriculum online with the use of technology. This structured approach ensured a range of instructional methods and provided learners with varied opportunities for engagement and learning.

Small groups based on learners’ abilities

Meanwhile, the small groups opened the opportunity for the teachers to address the learning needs and strengths of their learners more effectively, which lead to more meaningful and efficient learning experiences. This combination of flexible, diverse teaching methods and focused, tailored instruction exemplifies how DI can be applied in the classroom. Participants also highlighted that the small groups were organized based on skill levels and their specific needs:

- “I test and then I group them and then I meet with the teachers and we get on board with where they're at for groups and then we teach to each group according to skill level.” **P06**
- “WIN time, I put them in ability groups.” **P07**
- “So, because it's, I just do ELA, I test them um at the beginning of the year, middle of the year and progress managed to throughout on their phonic and decoding skills. And so then when I do their small group, it's based on how they tested on those skills um in whole group providing a lot more support to those who still aren't readers or writers.” **P10**
- “You have the small groups, you're able to focus more on what that group needs, [...], you're able to focus a lot more on different things with those levels.” **P12**
- “I work with students on whatever skill they're needing. [...] And so in my group, we work really rigorously, rigorously on those skills in that small group.” **P16**

Participants noted that WIN Time operated by grouping learners according to their skill levels. This approach allowed for tailored lesson adjustments and more personalized activities, addressing individual needs more effectively and maximizing each learner's potential.

From what the researcher has gathered, WIN Time was defined by two key components: the stations and the small groups. The stations were facilitated by individuals who hold numerous strategies and ways to present their lessons which allowed diversity in learning, exposing the learners to different approaches and giving a better chance for them to meet a style that fitted them the best.

Theme 3: Offering Multiple Learning Pathways

The education community was very lucky to have resources designed to enhance teaching efficacy and ultimately improve learning outcomes. Leveraging these resources was essential for teachers committed to delivering the highest quality education to their learners. At McLaughlin Elementary School, numerous teachers have skillfully integrated DI into their lessons, underscoring its significance in creating an inclusive and effective learning environment. By varying teaching techniques to accommodate different learning styles, these teachers ensured personalized attention and support for each learner, enhancing overall educational outcomes through modifications of either the lesson, instructions, or the activities they presented as they say the following:

- “We do sometimes we do completely different activities depending on what they need. Sometimes we do the same activity. But I, I uh make it easier for the kids who are struggling, the kids who can do more, we, we probably do more with it and kind of at a higher level.” **P03**
- “Our students are grouped into four groups and the lessons are modified based, based on students' needs. Yes. During when I assist all four groups of students and modify content when necessary.” **P08**
- “For example, for those who are advanced or those who are in the higher groups we are able to challenge them more so if our lessons are easy for them we can get to use the three next lessons to further challenge them. For those who are in the average or in the second group you just have to be so-so or the lessons are just the same.” **P11**
- “So this group like, let's say they may be struggling more with the reading. So I'd, I, I'd have to read the entire paragraph and the question that the and simply simplify it for them and even maybe do some sentence starters as well.” **P17**

It was highly commendable that certain teachers appreciated the significance of DI and seamlessly integrated it into their lessons, even without direct mandates. Their initiative to apply this method presented their commitment when it came to nurturing each learner's potential and enriching the overall educational experience, not only highlighting their adaptability and innovative mindset, but also reflecting a profound respect and empathy for their learners. From the strategies that they have shared, these teachers were not just performing their duties; they were exceeding expectations to ensure that the unique needs of every learner were addressed, thus creating a more inclusive and supportive learning environment.

According to Strogilos et al. (2020), teachers were encouraged to learn how to create appropriate modifications that align closely with standard classroom activities while still being tailored to meet the needs of their learners considering that the goal was to include these learners in general class activities without having to create a separate, overly specialized activities. This balance between making modifications and maintaining activity similarity should be a key component of both pre-service and in-service training for teachers (Strogilos et al., 2020). Such strategies connect to Bruner's theory which encourages teachers to continuously involve themselves in their lessons and provide the scaffolding that would help in facilitating the learning of their learners as they attempt to develop their skills further while not being overwhelmed by the complexity of these through simplification of activities, encouragement from their teachers, and other appropriate strategies (McLeod, 2023).

These statements underscored the remarkable adaptability and resourcefulness of teachers in employing techniques that suited their unique classroom dynamics or those they found more convenient and manageable. This act ensured that teaching methods were tailored from their individual experience to the specific needs of their learners, promoting an environment conducive to learning. There were teachers who have employed strategies in their classroom that promoted DI (P14, P15), while some were able to provide us a closer

look into the WIN Time program (P01, P05, P06, P07, P08, P10, P12, P16). There were also those who went out of their way to provide opportunities for more pathways in their class' learning through modifications (P03, P08, P11, P17).

DI has emerged as a pivotal strategy for creating inclusive learning environments, as it addressed the varied needs of learners, thereby enhancing their learning experiences and outcomes (Unal et al., 2022). Although this process can be challenging and time-consuming, embracing flexibility and continuously refining teaching methods ultimately benefited learners more than teachers. Just as learners worked in different ways, teachers were also capable of adapting their methods to meet the diverse educational needs of their learners (Killen & O'Toole, 2023).

Teachers' Experiences In Using DI

In order to truly appreciate the methods and gain a comprehensive idea of the DI, the researcher made an effort to know more about this approach and gather insights from those directly involved in implementing it. The aim of the queries was to explore how DI, including the WIN Time Program, was integrated into the school's learning setting and if it influenced the teaching practices and learner outcomes. The researcher was dedicated to uncover the practical realities of the program from the perspective of the teachers who execute it as well as DIs in general, thereby gaining a deeper appreciation of its operational dynamics and impact. In their discussion, these themes were brought up: Perceptions on DI and WIN Time Program, Implementation of DI, and Experiential Insights into DI.

Theme 1: Perceptions on DI and WIN Time Program

This theme delved into the diverse perceptions of the WIN Time program held by teachers. Much like a coin with two sides, the effectiveness and reception of WIN Time can vary based on individual experiences and perspectives. While the primary objective of WIN Time was to deliver DI tailored to meet the unique needs of each learner, opinions about its implementation and impact differ significantly.

For some, the WIN Time program was seen as a highly effective method for teachers to concentrate on the specific needs of their learners, enabling more targeted and personalized educational support. This positive perspective highlighted the potential of WIN Time in enhancing learner engagement and achievement through its focus on individualized instruction. These following participants appreciated how WIN Time allowed them to address varying learning styles and academic levels within the classroom, ultimately cultivating a more inclusive and supportive learning environment as what they say in the following statements:

- *“So with our school and our WIN time, I think it's huge because we're hitting those students' needs big time.” P08*
- *“I really enjoy it. You have the small groups, you're able to focus more on what that group needs, whether it's from CVC words to multisyllabic words to, yeah, you're able to focus a lot more on different things with those levels.” P12*
- *“I think that differentiated instruction is really important and I am glad that the school is having this WIN time because it allows us and the teachers to really focus and um assist those who are kind of struggling and then just you know, develop their skills.” P17*

It was immensely reassuring to find teachers who understood and appreciated the core aim of the WIN Time program, which was to view learners as individuals with varying levels of skills, even within the same grade. This recognition spoke volumes about their commitment to strengthening an inclusive and adaptive educational environment. These teachers saw the true essence of WIN Time which was addressing each learner's unique needs and providing tailored support to bridge any gaps in their learning journey— another perspective shared by teachers which revolved around the belief that the WIN Time approach enabled the school to effectively address learning disparities between different grade levels and among learners as stated by these participants:

- *“I just think it's very important because especially when we get to grades three through five because our gap is so much wider then. And that's like those critical years of the smarter balance testing and content that is just a lot more difficult than they've experienced K-2. And so being able to differentiate in 3, 4, 5 is crucial.” P10*
- *“And so I think that hour that we do small group is really helpful for the, the few who are on the lower end of the phonic skills because we're able to bridge that gap and meet them where they're at...” P16*

Educational gaps were no strangers to learning institutions, yet they presented opportunities for teachers to devise innovative methods to address them, such as the WIN Time program. As highlighted in the theme's introduction, differing opinions about the program's effectiveness were inevitable. While many teachers appreciated the concept and its potential to cater to individual learning needs, it was inevitable for different opinions to come to the table, including these teachers who appreciated the concept but found it difficult to implement:

- *“The What I Need time? Yeah. Um I like it. I like that. The kids are getting that but it's so it's also um it's hard to give every kid what they need because it's an hour and I have to structure my groups in a way that they all can have adequate time of learning.” P04*
- *“That is really my struggle every day every week it was a very challenging if only we could separate them I want to do so but they have to be included since it is inclusion.” P11*

– *“I like it, but I struggle with it because a lot of the things I learned- they say you shouldn't ability group students. But yet that's during whole group time and small groups, they do need certain skill knowledge. I have trouble because at this grade, I feel like they know what group they're in, they know if they're the high and they know if they're the low.” P15*

Opinions could often appear as a battle of ideas, but within this so-called battle laid the opportunity for discussions that drove innovation and enhancement of the program. Imagine, if all teachers shared the same perspective on the approach, it would likely become stagnant and resistant to constructive criticism. The diversity of comments and critiques about the WIN Time program was not just acceptable but essential for its improvement. By embracing a variety of viewpoints, the program could evolve and adapt to better meet the needs of both teachers and learners. This openness to feedback ensured that the WIN Time program remains dynamic and responsive, ultimately creating a more effective and inclusive educational environment.

There were teachers who asserted that integrating the WIN Time program into their classrooms allowed them to concentrate more effectively on the individualized needs of their learners (P08, P12, P17). Alhameedyeen (2023) underscored this sentiment by highlighting the strong preference among teachers for employing DI. This method, combined with a dedication to remaining updated on contemporary and pertinent teaching techniques, allowed teachers to meet the varied learning styles of their learners. As a result, teachers were able to create and present materials and activities that accommodated learners with various levels of ability and interests (Shareefa, 2020). This responsive approach not only enriched the educational experience but also ensured that instructional practices remained effective and engaging for all learners.

Additionally, several participants viewed the WIN Time program as a crucial tool for bridging learning gaps among learners (P10, P16). The unprecedented disruptions caused by factors such as the recent COVID-19 pandemic, alongside individual circumstances unique to each learner, have impeded academic progress for many learners. However, the implementation of WIN Time has led to notable improvements and heightened confidence among these learners. Teachers have observed significant strides as learners better align with the curriculum and achieve their academic potential (Shareefa, 2020). This program not only addressed immediate educational setbacks but also fostered a more resilient and adaptive learning environment, proving its vital role in supporting learners' recovery and growth.

Meanwhile, some teachers have expressed challenges in implementing the WIN Time program effectively within their classrooms (P04, P11, P15). These teachers have identified that the complexity of the concepts they were required to teach could significantly hinder their ability to differentiate instruction, thereby impacting their self-efficacy (Porta & Todd, 2023). The research conducted by Letzel et al. (2022) further revealed that while participants acknowledged the inherent value of DI, the scarcity of adequate resources complicated its application. Consequently, despite recognizing the potential benefits of this approach, the practical difficulties and resource constraints often undermined its successful integration into teaching practices.

In summary, the diverse opinions regarding the WIN Time program highlighted a crucial aspect of its development: the necessity for varied perspectives and constructive criticism. These challenges underscored the importance of continuous feedback and adaptation. By embracing a broad spectrum of viewpoints, the WIN Time program could better address its limitations, enhance its effectiveness, and ultimately create a more inclusive and supportive educational environment.

Theme 2: Implementation of DI

This theme addressed the application of DI by teachers, highlighting its critical role within the framework of the WIN (What I Need) Time program. This structured approach allowed teachers to effectively target individual learning needs, ensuring that each learner received the tailored support necessary for their academic growth.

However, DI meant a vast and multifaceted concept, encompassing a variety of techniques and interpretations. Many teachers anchored their DI practices on the screeners or assessments conducted by themselves or interventionists, allowing them to tailor their instruction to meet the specific needs of their learners such as these participants:

– *“During WIN time, students are grouped according to assessments conducted by the interventionist. [...] I created my WIN time instruction based on these assessments, selecting activities that cater to the specific needs of each student, thereby facilitating their growth and progress.” P02*

– *“And so then when I do their small group, it's based on how they tested on those skills um in whole group providing a lot more support to those who still aren't readers or writers.” P10*

– *“I have some screeners. Like today I'm doing a screener but oh my gosh, I get three done in an hour. So it's taking me a while to get through. These kids are showing growth on their screeners, which is good But um for math, I don't do four, I don't always do four separate levels. Sometimes I'll just do two.” P15*

Relying on valid data to inform teaching methods was a strategic approach, as this data was specifically designed to guide and enhance learner learning. By leveraging these insights, teachers created more targeted and effective instruction. On the other hand, a hands-on, intuitive approach to DI, where teachers adapted their strategies in real-time and immediately responded to the evolving needs of their learners through direct observation, was another respectable way of implementing DI, as done by the following teachers:

– “We do sometimes, we do completely different activities depending on what they need. Sometimes we do the same activity. But I, I uh make it easier for the kids who are struggling, the kids who can do more, we, we probably do more with it and kind of at a higher level.” **P03**

– “If they can read Decodables, they're reading Decodables. If they're working on, still working on some letters, I need to work on those letters if they're um, somewhere on the, the skill survey, if they're at CVC or uh blends or long vowels, vowel teams, you know, diagraphs.” **P06**

– “Our students are grouped into four groups and the lessons are modified based, based on students needs.” **P08**

Gathering assessments could be time-consuming and the process lengthy, making it immensely beneficial when teachers who implemented DI based on observations alone. This ability to quickly assess and adapt to the needs of their learners on the spot showcased a remarkable skill set. This dual approach ensured that the diverse needs of all learners were met with precision and care.

No two learners were ever identical; as they participated in their classes, they encountered lessons from teachers whose personal experiences, knowledge, and pedagogical approaches vary widely (Killen & O'Toole, 2023). This rich diversity among teachers significantly enhanced the learning environment, offering learners a complex and nuanced educational experience that drew from a broad spectrum of perspectives and methodologies.

When it came to implementing DI in the classroom, some teachers relied heavily on the screening and assessments available to them (P02, P10, P15). Research by Porta & Todd (2023) indicated that teachers are more effective in implementing differentiation when the learners' difficulties are recognized and documented by other professionals through thorough assessments and tests. This reliance on formal evaluations not only informed teachers about the specific needs of their learners but also provided a structured foundation upon which to base their instructional strategies. Consequently, leveraging these assessments enabled teachers to tailor their approaches more precisely, thereby enhancing the overall efficacy of DI in addressing individual learning challenges.

For some teachers, their approach to DI was meticulously crafted based on their personal insights and observations of their learners' needs (P06, P08). Research supported the notion that teachers often invest considerable effort in designing diverse and engaging activities that not only enhance lesson appeal but also catered to varied learning needs and adhered to required standards (Van Geel et al., 2022).

In essence, the dynamic nature of educational environments was reflected in the diverse approaches teachers took towards DI. As learners engaged in their classes, they benefited from the variety of experiences, knowledge, and pedagogical methods that teachers bring to their teaching (Killen & O'Toole, 2023). This diversity enriched the learning experience and helped cater to a range of learner needs and learning styles, creating a more inclusive educational setting. While some teachers depended on data-driven methods such as screenings and assessments to inform their DI strategies (P02, P10, P15), which research showed enhanced the effectiveness of differentiation (Porta & Todd, 2023), others relied on their keen observational insights to tailor their instruction (P06, P08). Research also highlighted that these teachers often design engaging and varied activities to boost motivation and address diverse learning needs (Van Geel et al., 2022). Nevertheless, both approaches, whether data-driven or reliant on keen observational insights, highlighted the versatility and dedication of teachers in their quest to provide the best possible educational experience.

Theme 3: Experiential Insights into DI

This theme explored the experiences of teachers as they implemented DI in their classrooms. Their experiences included the development of personalized learning activities, adjustments based on ongoing assessments, and the use of various instructional techniques to address different learning styles and abilities. Despite sharing a common goal of implementing DI, these variances lead to distinct challenges and triumphs for each teacher.

No matter how similar their strategies were to one another, teachers inevitably encountered unique experiences influenced by various factors, including the number of learners in their classroom and their diverse study habits, among others. Some participants have candidly admitted their doubts about the method, reflecting the complexities and uncertainties inherent in adapting to the ever-evolving needs of their learners which include the following teachers:

– “So they get 13 to 14 to 15 minutes of that CVC here. But then they also get it doubled when they move to her and then computer group. And I'm not so crazy about like, are they really working?” **P08**

– “I feel like I'm doing less small groups with fourth grade standards. And so I often feel like we have these big chunks of days where our kids are not even touching the standards that we are as teachers or as specific grade teachers are supposed to be, are supposed to be teaching.” **P14**

Worrying showed how one cared, in this case, it showed the dedication and seriousness the teachers had in order to provide the quality education their learners deserve. Their worries highlighted the complexities of DI and the continuous effort required to adapt and refine their approaches. Such expressions of concern were a testament to their unwavering commitment to their learners' success and well-being, showcasing the resilience and empathy that defined truly effective teachers. Additionally, some teachers have expressed how certain learners can be particularly challenging to manage during class:

– “Sometimes it gets up to be a little bit um chaotic when we’ve got so many different groups going and, but that, that’s just the way it is.” **P03**

– “Um, and that got, that was fine up until the point where the kids started destroying the cards that I was making them, they would just be destroyed like spit on, chewed on, torn.” **P04**

Being a teacher meant guiding numerous kids with different personalities, a reality that can indeed be difficult. It can get overwhelming, so it was truly worth mentioning how teachers stayed patient and firm despite the challenges they faced. For a change, this steadfast dedication was complemented by the teachers who found the practice of DI fulfilling which included these following participants:

– “Despite these demands, the payoff is significant. Over time, the growth of each learner becomes evident as I gradually provide the necessary support and challenges based on their unique capabilities, allowing them to progress at their own pace.” **P02**

– “I, I, it’s easier to see progress when you’re teaching small groups according to their skill, I can test them and I test them every two weeks and I see that growth and yeah, it’s fulfilling for me too.” **P06**

Improving oneself was not easy, so helping someone else become a better version of themselves through various efforts was truly worthwhile. Witnessing growth was indeed a joyous feeling, but being a contributor to that growth was even more fulfilling. These teachers may have encountered different sides of the journey, but at the end of the day, one thing remained the same: the learners were able to take another step forward because of their support. This shared progress reflected the profound impact of their commitment and passion for teaching.

In this study, some participants expressed hesitation and self-doubt about their approach to DI and whether they were effectively implementing it (P08, P14). As suggested by Porta et al. (2022), these negative feelings may have stemmed from frustrations encountered during the implementation process. Addressing these challenges could help teachers recognize the true value and enjoyment of DI. Uncertainty often acted as a barrier, undermining confidence and motivation; thus, when teachers were well-informed and clear about their methods, they were more likely to feel assured in their practices and more enthusiastic about the benefits of DI (Onyishi & Sefotho, 2020).

For some, being able to cater to one’s learners’ educational needs alone could be difficult, so if one did this for multiple learners at once, doing so can be chaotic or difficult to manage (P03, P04). According to Killen and O’Toole (2023), misbehavior was sometimes interpreted by teachers as an indication of the learner’s particular intelligence wherein those who always talk could possibly be a sign that a learner tends to be on being verbal or linguistic and interpersonal, made them more fit to do oral reports or group discussions. This brought us back to Howard Gardner’s (2021) belief that humans possessed different intelligences and described it as our means to deal with problems in one or more settings.

On a more positive note, some teachers found the implementation of DI deeply fulfilling and worthwhile (P02, P06). This satisfaction often stemmed from witnessing their learners achieve their goals and grew more enthusiastic about their learning. Specifically, teachers who employed DI reported significant improvements in learner happiness, attributable to the supportive learning environment they create (Nayman et al., 2022). This aligned with the findings of Porta & Todd (2022), who observed that teachers not only view DI as a method that fosters inclusivity through differentiated contexts, materials, and processes but also recognized the positive outcomes it generated for their learners. The rewarding nature of these outcomes reinforced the value of DI, affirming its impact on both teachers and learners.

With that said, while some participants in this study expressed hesitation and self-doubt regarding their implementation of DI (P08, P14), these feelings often arose from frustrations encountered during the process. Addressing these challenges and enhancing teachers’ clarity about their methods could help overcome uncertainty, which often undermined confidence and motivation (Porta et al., 2022; Onyishi & Sefotho, 2020). For teachers, managing the diverse educational needs of multiple learners was complex and chaotic (P03, P04), yet understanding that such misbehavior might reflected different types of intelligence, such as verbal or interpersonal, offered insights into more effective instructional strategies (Killen & O’Toole, 2023; Gardner, 2021). On the more positive side, many teachers found DI to be deeply rewarding and effective, noting improvements in learner enthusiasm and achievement (P02, P06). This satisfaction was largely attributed to the supportive learning environment created through DI, which aligned with research indicating that DI fosters inclusivity and generates positive outcomes for learners (Nayman et al., 2022; Porta & Todd, 2022). The positive experiences reported by teachers affirmed the significant impact of DI, highlighting its value in both enhancing learner learning and supporting teachers’ professional fulfillment.

Challenges Faced By Teachers In Implementing DI

A “one size fits all” approach to life was rarely effective and even impossible to achieve considering the inherent diversity of individual needs and circumstances. The researcher understood that this principle was also relevant when it came to the educational context, where each learner possessed a wide range of abilities, learning styles, and backgrounds. Understanding the importance and functions of an educational approach involved not only recognizing its benefits but also being aware of the gaps and challenges associated with its implementation which meant that every educational strategy, including DI, came with its own set of complexities and obstacles that can affect its effectiveness. Considering its goal, while DI had the potential to enhance learner achievement and learning outcomes, it

also presented its fair share of challenges. In exploring these challenges, the researcher met the following themes: Limited Time for Planning and Preparation, Ineffective Time Management and Implementation of WIN Time, and Issues on Class Management.

Theme 1: Limited Time for Planning and Preparation

This theme delved into the challenges teachers encountered during the planning and preparation phases for WIN (What I Need) Time. Implementing this method demanded meticulous planning, including tailoring learning activities to address the diverse needs of learners. Some participants highlighted the increased time required for planning and developing diverse activities as well as in preparing necessary materials, making the approach particularly challenging:

– *“While differentiated instruction is indeed highly effective in meeting the diverse needs of students, it poses challenges due to the increased time required for planning and preparing the necessary materials to support each student's individual goals.” P02*

– *“I wrote that down time to prepare different levels of activities for my different groups. I don't have a lot of time for that. And I think for like newer people, it's even harder.” P03*

– *“But the planning sometimes gets a lot. Yeah, it just gets a lot because you're differentiating for groups. And to me, your best teaching practice is not plan things, for me, is, I'm not a teacher that can plan things a week ahead because I like to see what happened and then change or extend or do what I have to do. [...] So I can't move on to something else.” P14*

Teachers meticulously analyzed assessment data and learner performance to develop tailored interventions and instructional strategies. This process demanded significant time and effort, ensuring that activities were precisely aligned with each learner's unique needs and learning goals. Such dedication highlighted the complexity and commitment required to effectively implement DI, ultimately fostering a more personalized and impactful educational experience for all learners.

One of the concerning challenges that teachers faced was how the implementation of DI demanded more time for activity or lesson planning and material preparation (P02, P03, P14). Porta & Todd (2022) acknowledged that while actual classroom instruction is crucial, the preparatory work, such as lesson reviews, goals and objectives, developing strategies, and planning instructional materials, was equally, if not more, essential. However, the detailed planning and preparation required for inclusive classes, combined with their existing workload, often left the teachers feeling overwhelmed by the pressures and demands of their responsibilities which in turn directly affected the quality of DI they deliver (Shareefa, 2020).

Theme 2: Ineffective Time Management and Implementation of WIN Time

This theme focused on the difficulties teachers faced with time management and the implementation of WIN (What I Need) Time. Teachers frequently encountered issues balancing the demands of WIN Time with their other teaching responsibilities. Coordinating the timing and structure of WIN sessions required careful planning to ensure that all learners received the targeted support they needed without disrupting the flow of the regular curriculum.

Some of the teachers have reported encountering time constraints when implementing WIN Time, as reflected in the following statements:

– *“So there aren't a ton of challenges. Um, ideally, I would have three groups. I would love to have 20 minutes per group. So the challenge for me is trying to fit everything into 15. And another challenge is keeping it at that 15. So if they didn't transfer well, and I'm down to 12.” P01*

– *“I guess that like every teacher's answer, I feel like there's more time. I just wish I had more time. I also wish I could do more groups.” P10*

– *“I almost wish we could split the groups out to where certain kids are getting more of what they need, but we don't have the time.” P12*

It was truly challenging for teachers when time constraints prevented them from accomplishing their planned lessons. This issue was compounded by factors beyond their control that impacted the allotted instructional time. Additionally, there were instances where standardized methods for testing and recording abilities were lacking, making it even more difficult for teachers to manage their time effectively and ensure that all learners' needs were met as mentioned by the following participants:

– *“Because it's so hard but to answer the next, using my assessments and seeing that there is growth is showing me that I think that's my biggest challenge.” P08*

– *“Oh one challenge that I keep bringing up to people. It's ELA is such a broad, it's not just reading and we have a school that focuses highly on reading. Now, the bad thing our kids are really behind in reading.” P14*

Implementing a project without clear guidance led to significant gaps in the outcomes, as it became challenging to measure progress and ensure the effectiveness of the methods used. Without proper tracking, it was nearly impossible for teachers to accurately identify and address their learners' needs. Therefore, standardized methods for testing and recording abilities were essential to provide a structured and reliable framework for evaluating learner progress and tailoring instruction accordingly.

A significant number of participants have also expressed concerns about the insufficient time allocated for the WIN Time program (P01, P10, P12). This lack of time was problematic because it led to teacher exhaustion and frustration, causing them to use the method less frequently and developed negative feelings towards the approach (Porta et al., 2022). As highlighted in the previous theme, the heavy workload of teachers was a major factor contributing to these challenges. With the constrained time they have in class, meeting the expectations set for WIN Time became nearly impossible (Yavuz, 2020).

Another challenge mentioned by the participants was the lack of efficient standardized methods or guidelines for implementing WIN Time (P08, P14). This included the absence of assessment tools that teachers can use to measure their learners' progress on specific subjects. According to Unal et al. (2022), it was crucial for school administration to identify and provide the support that teachers need to enhance the quality of education they deliver. This support could have included improved instructional resources and opportunities for teachers to collaborate and discuss strategies and methods, thereby uplifting each other and improving overall instructional effectiveness.

Ultimately, the implementation of the WIN Time program faced significant challenges, as expressed by many participants. The insufficient time allocated for WIN Time (P01, P10, P12) led to teacher exhaustion and frustration, resulting in less frequent use of the method and negative feelings toward it (Porta et al., 2022). The heavy workload of teachers further exacerbated these issues, making it nearly impossible to meet the expectations set for WIN Time within the constrained class time (Yavuz, 2020). Additionally, the lack of efficient standardized methods or guidelines for implementing WIN Time (P08, P14) hindered its effectiveness. This included the absence of assessment tools to measure learners' progress. As Unal et al. (2022) suggested, it is crucial for school officers to identify and provide the necessary support for teachers.

Theme 3: Issues on Class Management

This theme dug deeper into the complexities teachers faced in managing groups effectively, particularly during the implementation of DI in WIN (What I Need) Time. Balancing the needs of diverse learners within small groups or individual sessions could be particularly challenging. Teachers often grappled with organizing and maintaining productive group dynamics, ensuring that each learner received adequate attention and support while managing the flow of instruction. This highlighted the intricate task of coordinating group activities and interactions to meet varied educational needs while preserving an organized and focused classroom environment.

One recurring issue reported by participants was the lack of motivation among learners to engage with their work, adding another layer of difficulty to effective group management.

– *“And it's, I just don't know, like, what to give them as a reward because clearly the game isn't, not motivating them. A sticker chart is not motivating them, which you can tell on that door how many stickers those kids have. It is not working.” P04*

– *“...keeping them on task, um, when I'm working with the group and then I got two to three more groups that are working on other things.” P05*

– *“So what will happen is that [redacted] won't do any work since he doesn't understand he will not do anything but instead he will just play with blocks.” P11*

Dealing with learners' attitudes towards their work was a common challenge for teachers in the educational setting. Since outcomes were the direct result of learners' efforts, unaddressed disengagement posed a significant problem. Additionally, some teachers have expressed the need for more human resources in classrooms, as mentioned below:

– *“I feel it becomes challenging during whole group when I am alone with 19 students.” P07*

– *“We used to do what I liked uh one thing that we did used to do that, I do miss, we used to have an extra certified teacher per grade level. [...] So that is something I wish we could go back to is having that extra person.” P13*

– *“I think the biggest encounter when we do our groups or WIN time is when there are behaviors involved. [...] but we are thankful that the teachers are well equipped, well equipped and we also have other paras from our other department like the SpEd Department to help us through that.” P17*

The lack of adequate manpower and unbalanced ratio of teachers to the learners in the classroom caused issues in the implementation of DI, as teachers struggled to provide individualized attention and support to all learners, thereby compromising the overall effectiveness of the learning environment.

An observation that some of the participants had was how the learners lack motivation to engage with their tasks or cooperate in lessons (P04, P05, P11). Tomlinson et al. (2023) suggested that a learner's interest is closely tied to their motivation to learn and participate in lessons. This implied that if learners were interested in what the teacher was discussing, their motivation to engage will match that level of interest. Consequently, if teachers could successfully motivate their learners, the learners will make greater efforts and better understand the lessons (Tomlinson et al., 2023).

Additionally, teachers have expressed that implementing DI would be more manageable with increased human resources in the classroom (P07, P13, P17). Similar to the findings of Onyishi & Sefotho (2020), teachers in their research admitted that managing too

many children in one class was a significant challenge. Support from colleagues can greatly improve the quality of DI in the classroom, as well as the presence of a coach to assist in managing the class (Van Geel et al., 2022).

Ways In Resolving Challenges

An effective teacher could be characterized not only by their outstanding ability to design innovative and suitable lessons but also by their continuous adaptability and refinement of teaching strategies to cultivate an optimal learning environment. This adaptability was crucial when implementing DI within an inclusive setting, which called for intense planning when addressing the diverse needs of learners. To navigate the challenges they faced, they employed problem-solving techniques and made real-time adjustments, incorporating feedback and refining their methods as needed. The data gathered from the interviews led to the identification of the following themes: Setting Expectations, Reassignment of Small Groups, Collaborative teaching and Team Support, Enhancing Instructional Engagement, and Continuing Professional Development and Trainings.

Theme 1: Setting Expectations

Being a teacher has involved forming a trusting relationship with your learners. Thus, setting clear expectations and finding compromises in the classroom was essential. When both parties were aware of the tasks to be accomplished and the goals to be achieved, they could work together in sync, creating a solid foundation for mutual understanding and success. Several teachers have stated that they established clear expectations to effectively address the challenges they encountered, thereby nurturing a structured and supportive atmosphere for both teaching and learning:

– “You have to get this skill because in second grade you're gonna do this and this, I guess not just one thing you're doing both. Um, and then pretty soon you're not gonna need your 100 chart. Pretty soon, you're gonna be doing double-digit addition without a 100 chart. Because you know, ‘Oh yeah, I'm adding like 35. So that's three tens. Oh, 3 tens plus 43 is 73. I'm adding five more.’ You know, it's gonna be mental but you have to like practice through this a million times.” **P04**

– “What I've told them is if you're going to sleep, now you're gonna owe me some WIN time later on in the day while choice time thing and sometimes that shakes them out of that. [...] So it's using, utilizing that kind at the end of the day catch up if they're refusing to do whatever it is. And usually just to tell them that's what they're gonna do they're like, ok. And then they'll deal with it.” **P13**

When expectations were clearly defined, it supported the effective implementation of instructional strategies, including DI, and as a result, teachers were better able to execute their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of their learners since everyone has a shared understanding of the learning goals. This clarity not only aided in achieving educational objectives but also fostered a collaborative and supportive learning environment.

To support this, Burden (2020) emphasized the importance of establishing explicit expectations, rules, and procedures in the classroom to create a well-structured and focused educational experience which can help both the teachers and their learners to understand their roles and responsibilities more clearly, thereby facilitating a smoother educational process. By setting these clear expectations, teachers can more effectively guide their learners towards achieving educational objectives, reducing confusion and enhancing overall learning outcomes. Mofield (2019) echoed this view, noting that a commitment to collaboration and compromise within the classroom enhanced the effectiveness of DI by working together and adhering to well-established guidelines.

Theme 2: Reassignment of Small Groups

As educators endeavored to improve learning outcomes, they anticipated that learners will exhibit measurable progress in their skills over time and by regularly evaluating learner performance and refining their strategies, teachers created a supportive learning environment conducive to growth. As learners progressed, educators introduced increasingly complex concepts, fostering confidence and readiness for more challenging material. This continuous process highlighted the expectation that effective teaching practices and a responsive and adaptive learning environment, significantly enhanced learners' knowledge and abilities. To support this growth, some teachers have strategically opted to rearrange groups like the following participants:

– “I move groups around a lot, both with which students are in which group and when those groups come to me, due to observations, I try to keep a big gap between groups. So I'm trying to see the, the more challenged kids next to the need to be challenged kids.” **P01**

– “So really getting them to help each other in their group um first and then if they absolutely can't get it, they, they know that they can come ask me but they have to, they have to learn how to not interrupt.” **P05**

– “What my coach suggested, which I'm currently applying now, it's not really differentiated but it is for the whole group and that is during groupings, there should be at least one who knows what they're doing. That person should be placed in the center and then there should be students who are in lower levels.” **P11**

Considering their deep familiarity with their learners' levels, teachers made informed decisions about what was best for each learner. If a teacher identified that a particular learner would benefit more from being in a different group, they were moved accordingly to better support their learning. This flexibility and responsiveness underscored the teachers' commitment to personalized education.

Reorganizing small groups based on pre-assessments of learners' readiness levels and learning profiles has proven to be highly effective, as Mengistie (2020) underscored the necessity of tailoring instruction to meet individual needs. Mengistie (2020) highlighted that pre-assessment is vital in DI, enabling teachers to accurately identify each learner's readiness and learning profile to form the most suitable groups. Nonetheless, it was also crucial for educators to recognize and embrace the diversity within their classrooms, ensuring that they support and nurture each learner's inherent potential (Hasanah et al., 2022). Such a method is also a nod to Vygotsky's ZPD which mentions the need for the learner to be in a setting where they are challenged as an effort to push them from their current abilities and for them to understand the limits of their capabilities and skills (Zaretsky, 2021).

Theme 3: Enhancing Instructional Engagement

Continuous growth was essential not only for learners but also for teachers who were dedicated to lifelong learning. Their initiative to constantly explore and refine methods to better serve their learners was truly commendable. Such proactive engagement in refining instructional techniques and embracing new pedagogical approaches reflected a deep-seated dedication to enhancing educational experiences, ultimately leading to more effective and impactful learning environments. For these teachers, implementing engaging teaching strategies that were closely tied to their lessons was a key approach:

– *“So like, for example, we're learning about figurative language. I don't know when I had time to teach figurative language with the structure. But what I did is I did a matching game with the definition and the picture and the kids for morning meeting had to find their match.” P14*

– *“So it definitely helps with engagement, I noticed. Um manipulatives, like fraction tiles, we had fraction tiles out nonstop during fractions.” P15*

– *“So like for example, my challenge that I'm dealing with in the morning, I have a student who's working on phonemic awareness and he doesn't know all of his letters, he doesn't know all of his letter sounds, but the next group up they're working on digraphs. [...] So we start the group with phonemic awareness so that he can get the instruction that he really needs, so they can review the skill and then he just kind of tags along on their digraphs.” P16*

These methods not only enhanced the effectiveness of instruction but also captivated the learners' interests, showcasing the teachers' commitment to creating a dynamic and stimulating educational environment. Given the broad scope of DI, teachers had the flexibility to design and adapt various methods that best suit their particular educational contexts. This adaptability empowered teachers to innovate and utilize creative approaches in lesson delivery, ensuring that instructional methods were tailored to the diverse needs and preferences of their learners. Zerai et al. (2021) highlighted that the ability to customize and personalize teaching strategies is a fundamental strength of DI. Such flexibility enabled educators to craft engaging and comprehensible learning experiences, thereby enhancing learners' understanding of complex concepts and contributing to a more effective and meaningful educational process. Furthermore, continuously refining instructional methods to meet the evolving needs of the classroom ensured that teaching practices stayed relevant and impactful, as emphasized by Bondie et al. (2019). This dynamic approach not only supported diverse teaching strategies but also was a boost to learner engagement and comprehension, as noted by Zerai et al. (2021).

Theme 4: Collaborative Teaching and Team Support

Experience being the best mentor did not only encompass the experience of the teachers themselves but also the stories that their colleagues shared. Whether these interactions were from a planned discussion to a simple conversation over coffee, there were many instances for teachers to collaborate with each other. Using these opportunities truly benefitted one's practice as they incorporated the teachings and advice from the teachers who were part of their learning setting. Fortunately, such collaboration and support was present as stated by these participants:

– *“I really rely on a lot of both from [redacted] and [redacted], when they do their testing, then they present me with what the child is lacking and the groups are according to their skills, their levels. So then that's what I base it on and yeah, I just worked that way with them.” P12*

– *“And we had so many different varying levels and talking to [redacted] she was doing four groups successfully and she saw the benefits of that.” P13*

– *“[...] we are so thankful that our teachers are equipped to handle it. We have assistance from the SpEd department and the SpEd para. So the one on one support with some of our students who are in the IEPs that have behavior issues.” P17*

Surrounding yourself with individuals who share your goals was not only ideal but profoundly beneficial for both the school and its learners. While one brought unique ideas to the table, others contributed their insights, fostering collective growth and development. Nguyen and Ng (2020) emphasized that professional collaboration, particularly among teachers, typically unfolds in three stages: sharing, refining, and disseminating ideas.

This process began with collegial conversations and discussions, led to a thorough analysis of experiences, and ultimately progressed to the dissemination of effective techniques that other educators incorporated into their practice. This brought us back to Robertson (2021) whose study was built on Vygotsky's SCT wrote that purposeful collaboration among teachers, along with active involvement

from families and steadfast support from administrators, was essential for achieving optimal outcomes in young learners' transition processes.

Theme 5: Continuing Professional Development and Trainings

Furthermore, collaborative support among teachers, through sharing personal recommendations and insights, enhanced their ability to overcome obstacles and improved practice. This process of adjustment and mutual support ensured that DI remained effective and responsive.

Teachers have adopted strategic solutions to navigate and overcome the challenges of implementing DI, emphasizing adaptive methods that underscored their proactive efforts in addressing the complexities inherent in DI. This approach illustrated how educators continuously refined their practices by developing their professional skills in order to create a more responsive and supportive learning environment, ultimately enhancing educational outcomes for all learners. Some teachers have gone above and beyond by making extra efforts to plan ahead and refine their instructional methods, continually seeking ways to enhance their teaching practices and better meet the needs of their learners such as these participants:

– *“To address the challenges of implementing differentiated instruction, I took positive steps to plan ahead and manage my time efficiently. By prioritizing tasks and utilizing available resources effectively, I ensured that I could give adequate attention to preparing materials made to each student's needs.” P02*

– *“I think my biggest thing was at the beginning of the year was finding the right thing to use because coming in as a fresh teacher, um, I didn't have the training and stuff, you know, I think that was the biggest thing for me and then I reached out to our reading coach and just finding something that I could follow that was also going to meet their needs and that was using Ufli.” P08*

Lifelong learning has stayed relevant for a long time in this dynamic and changing world. In order to keep up with the trends of today, it was imperative for our teachers to continuously seek opportunities to grow as professionals. Oates (2023) stated that in the context of 21st-century education, it was crucial for teachers to be adept in DI to address the varied needs of a diverse learner population. Participation in professional development programs played a vital role in this process, as it equipped educators with advanced teaching strategies and tools, thereby enhancing their effectiveness and improving educational outcomes for learners (Porta et al., 2022). In an inclusive setting, it was essential for teachers to master differentiation as a key strategy for enhancing learners' learning experiences. This involved a continuous process of refining instructional methods based on the evolving needs of the class, ensuring that teaching practices remained relevant and effective for all learners (Bondie et al., 2019).

The responses from this study's participants revealed a profound dedication to enhancing classroom learning outcomes and supporting learner growth. Teachers demonstrated their commitment by building strong, respectful relationships with learners and setting clear expectations (P04, P13). They also strived to find the best arrangement for their learners to create engaging and effective learning environments (P01, P05, P11, P14, P15, P16). There were participants who actively worked collaboratively with their colleagues in order to improve each other's practices (P12, P13, P17). Additionally, these educators engaged in self-reflection and personal development to continually improve their teaching practices (P02, P08). Such efforts underscored their commitment to DI and their adaptability in meeting diverse learner needs.

Maintaining a consistent approach to DI enabled teachers to address the varied needs of their learners effectively, leading to enriched educational experiences and significant academic progress. The long-term impact of sustained DI practices was considerable, as they not only drove immediate learning improvements but also fostered the development of essential skills and resilience in learners. By adhering to a stable and ongoing application of differentiated strategies, teachers equip learners with the tools to become capable, confident individuals, prepared to succeed as productive members of society.

The researcher conducted three cycles of iterative comparison to enhance clarity and refine the findings from the collected data. In the first cycle, initial themes were identified based on the most apparent patterns in the participants' responses. During the second cycle, the researcher revisited the interview data to further categorize participants' answers, focusing on their professional experiences, teaching strategies, instructional practices, and perspectives on DI. Additionally, the challenges faced by teachers in implementing DI and the solutions they employed were thoroughly examined. In the final cycle, the cluster and emerging themes were further refined, ensuring a comprehensive and nuanced interpretation, as presented in this chapter. To synthesize the findings, a schematic diagram was created, encapsulating the themes identified from participants' responses and offering a coherent summary of the study's principal insights and conclusions.

Based on the data gathered, findings are herein presented.

On DI as practiced by teachers and other personnel at McLaughlin Elementary School, four themes were formulated and subthemes were also revealed, hence; Theme 1- Strategies for Optimizing Learning Outcomes with four sub themes such as hands on learning, art integration, Project Based Learning, and Low floor, High ceiling. Theme 2- Implementation of the WIN Time Program has two sub themes such as Different Learning Stations and Small groups based on learners' abilities; and Theme 3- Offering Multiple Learning Pathways does not have subthemes. On teachers' experiences in using DI, three themes emerged such as Perceptions on DI and WIN Time Program, Implementation of DI, and Experiential Insights into DI.

On challenges faced by teachers in implementing DI, these themes emerged: Limited Time for Planning and Preparation, Ineffective Time Management and Implementation of WIN Time, and Issues on Class Management.

On how these challenges were resolved by the teachers, these five themes were revealed: Setting Expectations, Reassignment of Small Groups, Collaborative teaching and Team Support, Enhancing Instructional Engagement, and Continuing Professional Development and Trainings.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of Themes

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, a conclusion is drawn.

DI, as employed by teachers and staff at McLaughlin Elementary School, though found to be overwhelming and chaotic, teachers recognized its values despite the challenges. Key difficulties identified include limited time for planning and implementation, vague guidelines, working with unmotivated learners, and insufficient human resources are also some of the challenges.

Drawing from the study's findings, these recommendations are proposed for different stakeholders involved in the research who are as follows:

For the Department of Education, leverage the findings of this study to inform and refine policies that enhance the implementation of differentiated instruction across various educational levels.

For school administrators, use the insights from this research to review and improve the current methods and practices within your school, aiming to elevate the quality of education through effective DI implementation.

For McLaughlin Elementary School should consider the following: allocate reasonable time for planning and implementation; provide a framework and guidelines; promote professional development through trainings or coaching; balance out teacher to learners' ratio; and consistently review and improve their methods.

For special education teachers, familiarize yourself with the aspects of differentiated instruction discussed in this study to further enrich

your knowledge and advance your professional development.

For general education teachers, recognize the significance of differentiated instruction and collaborate with special education teachers and interventionists to integrate DI effectively into your classroom practices.

For learners with special educational needs (LSEs), understand the benefits of differentiated instruction and how it can support and enhance your learning experience.

For Bachelor of Special Needs Education students, utilize this study as a resource to develop your teaching philosophies and ideas as you prepare for a career in education.

For parents and families, engage with your children's teachers to explore how you can support their learning at home and contribute to their educational progress.

For the researcher, conduct follow-up studies to assess any changes or improvements in DI practices within the school and identify areas that may require further investigation.

For future researchers, investigate DI methods in various schools, both within the same state and across different states, to compare practices, experiences, and challenges, ultimately contributing to a broader understanding and improved public perception of differentiated instruction.

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